

Enhanced Fenton-like catalytic performance of N-doped graphene quantum dots incorporated CuCo₂O₄

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Abstract

In the present study, a novel nanocomposite based on CuCo₂O₄ and N-doped graphene quantum dots (N-GQDs) as an iron-free heterogeneous Fenton-like catalyst was prepared by a two-step solvothermal method. Surface morphology, chemical structure, crystal phase, surface area and the pore size distribution of the synthesized nanocomposite were characterized with field-emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM), energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), X-ray diffraction (XRD), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), high resolution transmittance electron microscopy (HRTEH) and N₂ adsorption-desorption analysis. The results showed that N-GQDs play a significant role in the enhancement of catalytic degradation of methylene blue (MB) as a model contaminant. CuCo₂O₄/N-GQDs nanocomposite exhibited higher degradation rate of about 47 times higher than that of pristine CuCo₂O₄. This promotion can be attributed to the higher surface area of CuCo₂O₄/N-GQDs nanocomposite compared to pristine CuCo₂O₄ as well as the synergistic effects between N-GQDs and CuCo₂O₄. The effects of pH, catalyst mass and the initial concentration of H₂O₂ on the catalytic degradation of MB were investigated using Box-Behnken design. Finally, the dominant reactive oxygen species generated in the degradation process were identified and the possible mechanism for the catalytic degradation of MB was proposed.

Keywords: Methylene Blue, CuCo₂O₄, Nitrogen doped graphene quantum dots, Heterogeneous Fenton-like reaction

1. Introduction

One of the most common sources of pollutants discharged by different textile industries into the wastewater are organic dyes. Discharges of these organic pollutants with severe color, high toxicity and low biodegradability properties into wastewater without adequate treatment can cause serious health and environmental problems. There are a variety of processes available, depending on the kind of dye, for the removal of organic dyes by physical and chemical treatment technologies including coagulation, adsorption and membrane process. However, these conventional methods cannot be used effectively to remove dyes from wastewater. An efficient group of methods that have been successfully used to remove synthetic dyes from wastewater is advanced oxidation processes (AOPs).

Fenton method, one of the most popular advanced oxidation processes, is a catalytic process that utilizes hydrogen peroxide as an oxidant and dissolved ferrous salts as a homogeneous catalyst. Iron-free heterogeneous Fenton-like systems for activating H_2O_2 in AOP based have been proposed ¹¹. Among all the catalysts, copper- and cobalt-containing catalysts have attracted more attention recently, because of high electrical conductivity and high electrochemical activity of copper and cobalt, respectively. However, Cu/Co-based catalysts exhibit weak catalytic activities, which limit their practical applications in Fenton-like processes. Therefore, one the most important challenges in Fenton-like processes is the construction of catalysts with high activity, better stability and reusability.

Graphene quantum dots (GQDs) are a new class of zero dimensional carbon materials that exhibit properties of graphene and carbon dots. Combining the structure of graphene with carbogenic origin and quantum nature of carbon dots causes GQDs to show novel chemical/physical properties. In the recent years, carbon materials such as carbon dots ²⁴, graphene, graphitic carbon nitride ²⁶ and carbon quantum dots have been introduced into metal oxides to improve the catalytic, photocatalytic or photoelectrocatalytic performances of nanocomposites. These results suggest that GQDs play a significant role in the improvement of catalytic performance, and the combination of GQDs - metal oxide systems can be regarded as an effective strategy to construct more efficient catalysts.

In this work, a novel nanocomposite based on CuCo_2O_4 , and nitrogen doped graphene quantum dots (N-GQDs) was synthesized by a simple two-step solvothermal method and was used as a high-performance heterogeneous Fenton-like catalyst for the degradation of methylene blue (MB) as model contaminant. FE-SEM, N_2 adsorption-desorption analysis, FT-IR, XRD, XPS and HRTEM were employed to identify the morphology, structure, and the crystal phase of the prepared samples. The role of N-GQDs on the improvement of catalytic performance of prepared nanocomposite was studied in detail. The effects of pH, catalyst mass and the initial concentration of H_2O_2 on the catalytic degradation of MB were investigated using Box–Behnken design. Moreover, the dominant reactive oxygen species generated in the degradation process were identified and the possible mechanism for the catalytic degradation of MB over $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ was proposed.

2. Experimental section

Synthesis of N-GQDs

N-doped graphene quantum dots (N-GQDs) were prepared according to a previously reported procedure with a little modification. Typically, 0.84 g of citric acid and 0.72 g of urea was dissolved in 20.0 mL aqueous solution, and the resulted solution was stirred for 5 min to obtain a clear solution. The solution was transferred into a 50-ml Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and heated at 160°C for 8 h. Finally, 10 mL of ethanol was added to the resultant solution and the mixture was centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 15 min.

Synthesis of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$

CuCo_2O_4 was prepared by a simple solvothermal method. In a typical synthesis, 1.5 mL of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.24 mol/L) and 3.0 mL of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.24 mol/L) were added to 42 mL of ethanol and stirred for 30 min. Then, 3.0 mL of concentrated NH_4OH solution (25%) was added to the mixture and stirred for another 60 min. Then, the mixture was transferred to a 100-ml Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and heated at 180°C for 5 h. Finally, the product was washed three times with distilled water and dried at room temperature for 24 h. For the preparation of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NGQDs}$ nanocomposite, the procedure was as the same as CuCo_2O_4 synthesis, except that in a 42-mL ethanolic solution of Cu^{2+} and Co^{2+} , 1.0 mL of NGQDs solution was added.

Catalytic activity tests

The Catalytic activity of the catalysts for the degradation of MB was evaluated in a batch system. Typically, 50.0 mL of MB solution (5.0 mg/L) was added to a glass thermostated reactor (25.0 °C) together with 0.2 mL of 30% H₂O₂. Then, 5.0 mg of catalyst (CuCo₂O₄ or CuCo₂O₄/N-GQDs) was added to the solution and the mixture was stirred. To avoid any influence of ambient light, all reactions were carried out in a dark situation. The absorbance spectra were recorded in the wavelength range of 400–750 nm every 5 min until 35 min.

Experimental design and optimization

In order to obtain the best reaction conditions for the degradation of MB, the impacts of the catalyst mass (mg), pH and the initial concentration of H₂O₂ (mol/L) on the catalytic performance of CuCo₂O₄/N-GQDs for the degradation of MB were investigated. A three-factor, three levels Box–Behnken design was employed in order to achieve the highest degradation reaction rate constant (*k*_{obs}). Catalyst mass, pH and the initial concentration of H₂O₂ were investigated as independent variables and rate constant of the MB degradation was considered as the dependent variable. The experimental dominions of these factors were established as preliminary experiments. The variables and levels of the Box–Behnken design model are given in Table S1 (Supplementary Information). The polynomial equation generated by this experimental design is as follows:

$$y = \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i x_i + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{ii} x_i^2 + \sum_{1 \leq i < j}^n \beta_{ij} x_i x_j + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

where, *y* is the estimated response (dependent variable); *x_i* and *x_j* the coded variables of the independent variables; β_0 the constant, β_i the linear coefficient, β_{ii} the quadratic coefficient, β_{ij} the interactive coefficient and ε is a random error.

3. Results and Discussion

Spectroscopy and morphology characterization of nanocatalysts

The N-GQDs were synthesized by a facile hydrothermal method at 180°C. N-GQDs were hydrothermally synthesized by using citric acid and urea as carbon and nitrogen sources, respectively. In the hydrothermal conditions, citric acid and urea species react with each other

and citric acid amide molecules are formed. Then, citric acid amide molecules are self-assembled and nanosheet structures are formed. N-doped GQDs with nitrogen- and oxygen-containing groups can be formed by intramolecular dehydration and deammoniation of neighbor citric acid amide molecules.

The absorbance -and photoluminescence (PL) spectra of N-GQDs are shown in **Fig. 1**. As it is clear, N-GQDs absorption spectra shows two clear absorption bands at 234 and 337 nm and a broad peak at around 600 nm. The origins of the peaks at 234 nm and 337 nm are due to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of C=C and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the C=O, respectively^{28, 31}. The inset in Fig. 1 shows the photograph of N-GQDs solution under sun-light, indicating the intense absorption of light in visible region, consistent with the absorption spectra measurements. Similar to the most fluorescent carbon-based nanomaterials, the solution of N-GQDs emits blue light ($\lambda_{PL}=450$ nm) when excited with 360 nm (Fig. 1). The origins of the PL spectra of N-GQDs species is probably due to the effects of size and the surface functional groups in N-GQDs³².

Fig. 1

FT-IR spectroscopy was used to confirm the formation of N-GQD, CuCo₂O₄ and CuCo₂O₄/N-GQD. FT-IR spectrum of N-GQD (**Fig. 2**) indicates two bands at 3432 cm⁻¹ and 3316 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to N-H and O-H vibrations, respectively. The strong band at 1579 cm⁻¹ is the vibrational absorption band of C=C and the peak occurring at 1401 cm⁻¹ belong to the bending vibrations of C-N. These results reveal that there are large numbers of amine and hydroxyl groups exist on the surface of N-GQDs. The stretching vibration modes of the metal-oxygen bonds are found in the region lower than 750 cm⁻¹, and these can be used to confirm the formation of the metal oxide. The bands at 1577 cm⁻¹ and 1417 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the C=C and C-N vibrations and the bands at 661 cm⁻¹ and 582 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the spinel structure vibrations, respectively, confirm that CuCo₂O₄ and N-GQDs are present in the prepared CuCo₂O₄/N-GQD nanocomposite.

Fig. 2

XRD patterns of pristine CuCo_2O_4 and $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ are shown in **Fig. 3**. The distinct peaks appeared at 2θ values of 19.1° , 31.3° , 36.8° , 38.9° , 44.7° , 55.5° , 59.3° , 65.2° and 77.3° attributed to (111), (220), (311), (222), (400), (422), (511), (444), and (533) crystal planes, respectively, and the pattern was indexed to the cubic spinel crystal phase of CuCo_2O_4 with the space group of $\text{Fd}\bar{3}\text{m}$ (JCPDS file No. 78–2177).

Fig. 3

The surface morphology and the elemental composition of prepared catalysts were studied by FE-SEM and EDS. The FE-SEM images of catalysts are shown in **Fig. 4**. As shown in Fig. 4a, the morphology of pristine CuCo_2O_4 is hollow sphere with a relative uniform distribution and severe aggregation. The size of nanospheres is estimated to be about 25 nm. In the presence of N-GQD, the morphology of nanocomposite turns to the 3D flower-like hierarchical structure. The flower-like morphology was composed of a large number of multiple randomly assembled irregular-shaped sheets with a thickness of about 10 nm. The presence of two elements (i.e. C and N) in EDS spectrum (**Fig. 4**) confirmed the presence of N-GQDs in the $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ nanocomposite.

Fig. 5a shows HRTEM image of QGDs with the lattice spacing of around 0.24 nm, which agrees well with (100) spacing of graphitic carbon. As discussed, FE-SEM images of CuCo_2O_4 and $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQD}$ nanocomposites confirmed that the morphology of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQD}$ is quite different from that of CuCo_2O_4 grown by hydrothermal method under the same experimental conditions. The images clearly show the different morphologies for CuCo_2O_4 nanoparticulates (**Fig. 5b**) and nanoflakes of flowerlike $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQD}$ (**Fig. 5c**).

Fig. 4 and Fig. 5

The surface chemical composition of the synthesized $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ nanocomposite was characterized by XPS as shown in **Fig. 6**. A full XPS spectrum (survey spectrum) of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ surface in Fig. 6a indicates the presence of Co, O, Cu, N and C elements in $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ nanocomposite. Two major peaks with binding energies at 796.7 eV and 781.1 eV are observed for Co 2p curve at Fig. 6b, corresponding to the Co $2p_{1/2}$ and Co $2p_{3/2}$

spin-orbit peaks, respectively^{29, 42}. The Co 2p_{3/2} spectrum was fitted with two spin orbit doublets at 781.36 eV assigned to Co²⁺ components at tetrahedral sites and 779.9 eV assigned to Co³⁺ components at octahedral sites, and three satellite peaks I, II and III assigned to Co²⁺ and Co³⁺ components and are all in agreement with the results reported in literature^{29, 43}. For Co 2p_{1/2} XPS spectrum, the similar fitting was also done. The ratio of Co²⁺ to Co³⁺ ions in CuCo₂O₄/N-GQDs nanocomposite was calculated from deconvoluted data and obtained to be 1.7 and is in agreement with literature^{29, 42}. The Co 2p_{3/2}-2p_{1/2} spin-orbit splitting characteristic of the Co²⁺ and Co³⁺ species are almost identical for both oxides and are in agreement with the results reported in literature^{29, 42, 43}. Fig. 6c shows the Cu 2p XPS spectrum for CuCo₂O₄/N-GQDs nanocomposite. The Cu 2p spectrum is deconvoluted into several components due to Cu oxides and was fitted with three spin orbit doublets assigned to Cu⁺, Cu²⁺ and Cu³⁺ and two satellite peaks I and II. The components at 932.5 eV, 934.6 eV and 937.0 eV correspond to Cu⁺ at the tetrahedral sites, Cu²⁺ and Cu³⁺ at the octahedral sites, respectively and are in agreement with the results reported in literature⁴². Cu⁺ ions is seems to be due to the X-ray induced reduction of Cu²⁺ ions⁴⁴. The presence of paramagnetic Cu²⁺ species is revealed by the intense satellite peaks at 943.9 and 954.2 eV. The most prominent peak in Cu 2p spectrum is at 934.6 eV, which indicates the majority of Cu²⁺ at more energetically stable structure of octahedral sites^{29, 44}. Based on the deconvoluted Co and Cu curve regions, the ratio of Co²⁺/Co³⁺ and Co²⁺/Cu²⁺ ions in CuCo₂O₄/N-GQDs are 1.7 and 12.2, respectively which shows that Co²⁺ ions are partially substituted by Cu²⁺ ions.

Fig. 6

Fig. 6d shows XPS window of C 1s core level. This spectrum exhibits two main peaks centered at 284.8 (named as A) and 288.6 eV (named as B), which are attributed to carbon-carbon and carbon-oxygen bonds, respectively. The A peak has been deconvoluted to two peaks with binding energy (BE) of 284.8 and 286.1 eV which are attributed to C-C and C=C bonds of N-GQDs, respectively. The peak B has been curve fitted by a peak located at BE value of 288.7 which is assigned to carbon-oxygen (C-O) bond. The presence of peak B (carbon-oxygen bonds) with remarkable intensity as compared to peak A (carbon-carbon bonds) with the ratio of 0.57 revealed that the chemical bonds exist between C atoms of N-GQDs and O atoms of CuCo₂O₄.

Chemical bond formation between CuCo_2O_4 and N-GQDs molecules can also be verified through investigation of O 1s XPS window (Fig. 6e).

The deconvolution peaks of the O 1s spectrum are also resolved into three components, centered at 529.8, 531.6 and 533.3 eV, respectively (Fig. 6e). The low BE component observed at 529.8 eV is attributed to lattice O^{2-} forming oxide with cobalt and copper elements. The components observed at 531.6 and 533.3 eV are attributed to C-O and surface H_2O (physically adsorbed), respectively. It is also obvious that the oxygen-carbon bonds have noticeable contribution in O 1s spectrum. Therefore, O 1s XPS window curve fitting confirmed again the formation of carbon-oxygen chemical bonds. The deconvolution peaks of the N 1s spectrum are also resolved into three components including pyridinic N component at 398.2 eV, pyrrolic N component at 399.2 eV and substitutional component at 400.2 eV (Fig. 6f) and are in agreement with literature^{29, 48}.

Finally, the BET (Brunauer–Emmett–Teller) surface areas (S_{BET}) and the porous structures of the synthesized samples were investigated by nitrogen adsorption–desorption measurements. Adsorption equilibriums were displayed by isotherm curves regularly. The nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherms and the corresponding pore size distribution curves by the BJH method of the all samples are shown in **Fig. 7**.

As it is clear from the results (Table 1), S_{BET} of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NGQDs}$ nanocomposite ($105.67 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$) was significantly increased ($\sim 43\%$) by the incorporation of N-GQDs into the CuCo_2O_4 (with S_{BET} of $74.29 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$). The result of BJH analysis of CuCo_2O_4 in Fig. 7b shows that it possesses pores in the range of 1.70 to 10 nm, and strong peaks are observed at the pore diameters around 1.85, 4.61 and 6.05 nm. The pore-size distribution of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ was also obtained from the BJH analysis and showed that most of the pores were in the range of 1.21 to 20 nm, and strong peaks are observed at pore diameters around 1.21, 4.61 and 6.05, 9.22 and 18.93 nm.

Fig. 7

Table 1. Specific surface area, pore volume, average pore size, PZC of prepared samples.

samples	S_{BET} (m^2/g)	Pore volume (cm^3/g)	Pore size (nm)
CuCo_2O_4	74.29	0.19	10.52
$\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GCD}$	105.67	0.3	9.84

Fenton catalytic activity of prepared catalysts

The catalytic activities of CuCo_2O_4 and $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ catalysts were compared by plotting C_t/C_0 ratio as a function of reaction time (**Fig. 8**). As it is clear, $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ nanocomposite performed much more efficiently than pristine CuCo_2O_4 . The degradation efficiency of CuCo_2O_4 in MB degradation by hydrogen peroxide after 35 min is below 10%. Amazingly, when $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ was used as a catalyst in the reaction mixture, 96.4 % of MB was degraded in 35 min. The observed rate constant of the catalytic degradation of MB (k_{obs} , min^{-1}) in the presence of the $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ as catalyst is 0.094 min^{-1} (**Fig. 8d**), which is 47 times higher than that of CuCo_2O_4 ($k_{\text{obs}}=0.002 \text{ min}^{-1}$). The higher catalytic activity of the $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ nanocomposite compared to CuCo_2O_4 can be attributed to the higher surface area that provides more active sites for dye degradation. However, the increase in catalytic activity of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ is not only attributed to its higher surface area, because as discussed, S_{BET} of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{NGQDs}$ nanocomposite was increased about 43% (or 1.43 times higher) by the incorporation of N-GQDs into the CuCo_2O_4 , while its catalytic activity is about 47 times higher than that of pristine CuCo_2O_4 .

Fig. 8

The main reason for increase in the catalytic activity of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ nanocomposite compared to CuCo_2O_4 can be attributed to the enhanced electron transport kinetics between N-doped GQDs and metal ions including Cu and Co. This leads to these metal ions to be tightly attached to the surface of N-GQDs, which enhances the electron transport kinetics between N-

GQDs and metal ions. To understand the synergistic effects of N-GQDs and CuCo₂O₄, an in-situ experiment was designed.

Implication of active species in Fenton process

The most common active species in Fenton-like processes are hydroxyl radical ($\cdot\text{OH}$) and superoxide radical anions ($\cdot\text{O}_2^-$). The hydroxyl radical is a strong oxidizing agent ($E^0(\cdot\text{OH}/\text{H}_2\text{O}) = 2.8 \text{ V vs. NHE}$) that is able to degrade toxic and pollutant compounds. $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ radical anions are produced by the addition of one electron to molecular oxygen, and able to react with a variety of substances. To identify the active species involved in the degradation of MB over CuCo₂O₄/N-GQDs nanocomposite, a series of scavengers were utilized. tert-Butyl alcohol (TBA) and potassium iodide (KI) were employed as the scavengers of $\cdot\text{OH}$ in bulk ($\cdot\text{OH}_{\text{free}}$) and on the catalyst surface ($\cdot\text{OH}_{\text{ads}}$), respectively. Literature reveals that TBA reacts immediately with $\cdot\text{OH}$ species present in the solution ($k_{\cdot\text{OH}} = 5.2 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$). However, CHCl₃ reacts more rapidly with $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ ($k_{\cdot\text{OH}} = 5.2 \times 10^8 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$) than it does with $\cdot\text{OH}$ ($k_{\cdot\text{OH}} = 7.0 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$). Based on these evidences, TBA and CHCl₃ were used as scavengers of $\cdot\text{OH}$ and $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$, respectively. As shown in Fig. 9a, the MB degradation efficiency in 35 min reached above 96% in the absence of the scavengers. When TBA was added (0.5 mmol/L and 3.0 mmol/L) to the reaction vessel including MB, the degradation efficiencies within 35 min decreased to 45.0% and 35.0%, respectively. Also, when KI was added to the reaction vessel, the degradation efficiencies decreased from 96.4% to 37.0% and 26.0%, in the presence of KI from 0 to 0.5 mmol/L and 3 mmol/L, respectively (Fig.9b). These results demonstrate that MB was mainly degraded by the attack of $\cdot\text{HO}$ radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}_{\text{free}}$ and $\cdot\text{OH}_{\text{ads}}$) and $\cdot\text{HO}$ species (especially $\cdot\text{OH}_{\text{ads}}$) is the dominant reactive oxygen species in the CuCo₂O₄/N-GQDs system.

Fig. 9

To investigate the role of superoxide radical anions during the MB degradation, chloroform (CHCl₃) was applied as an $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ scavenger. As can be seen from Fig. 9c, the degradation efficiency of MB during the reaction time (35 min) was decreased from 96.4% to 86% and 52% as the CHCl₃ concentration was increased from 0 to 0.5 mmol/L and 3.0 mmol/L, respectively. The decrease in the degradation efficiency of MB with increasing CHCl₃ suggested that,

although $\cdot\text{O}_2^-$ was formed in the system, but its role in promoting the degradation of MB is limited relative to hydroxyl radicals, $\cdot\text{HO}$.

To further confirm the existence of $\cdot\text{HO}$ radicals, hydroxyl radicals generated on a $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ nanocomposite were identified by a photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy using terephthalic acid (TA) as a probe molecule, which reacted with $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals to produce highly fluorescent product, 2-hydroxyterephthalic acid (TAOH). The maximum PL intensity of TAOH at around 425 nm and is proportion to the amount of produced $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals. Fig. S1 (Supplementary Information) shows the PL spectra of the TA solution after reaction with H_2O_2 for 2 and 5 min over $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$. As shown in Fig. S1 (Supplementary Information), PL intensity increased with increasing reaction time, which indicated that the $\cdot\text{OH}$ radicals formed gradually in the presence of nanocatalyst and these radicals are the main active species in the degradation process of MB.

Optimization of the degradation of MB by $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$

The optimization step of the MB degradation onto $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ was performed using a Box–Behnken design. According to the reports of previous studies, the pseudo first-order kinetic model is used extensively in the heterogeneous Fenton-like processes. The pseudo first-order kinetic model is described by the Eq. (2):

$$\ln \frac{[C]_t}{[C]_0} = -k_{obs}t \quad (2)$$

where $[C]_t$ is the concentration of the MB at time t and $[C]_0$ is the initial concentration of the MB. The constant k_{obs} is the observed rate constant (1/min), which can be determined from the slope of the linear plot of $\ln \frac{[C]_t}{[C]_0}$ vs. t . By plotting $\ln \frac{[C]_t}{[C]_0}$ vs. t , it was obtained that MB degradation by H_2O_2 on $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ catalyst followed pseudo-first-order kinetic. The design matrix and the corresponding results of BBD experiments to determine the influences of the three variables including catalyst mass, pH and the initial concentration of H_2O_2 (ml) are presented in Table S2 (Supplementary Information). An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out in order to evaluate the significance of the model and of the parameters. The values of probability (P-values) were used as a tool to check the significance of each parameter. The P-values less than 0.05 imply that corresponding coefficient terms are statistically significant⁵⁶.

Based on the ANOVA analysis, X_1 , X_2 , X_3 , X_1X_2 , X_1X_3 and X_2X_3 are significant model terms for the degradation of MB. The mathematical equation relating the observed rate constant of MB degradation (Y) and significant independent variables is expressed by the following equation:

$$Y = 0.03633 + 0.02475x_1 + 0.02287x_2 + 0.01938x_3 + 0.01350x_1x_2 + 0.01800x_1x_3 + 0.01375x_2x_3 \quad (3)$$

where, as it was noted in Table 1, x_1 , x_2 and x_3 denote coded values of the pH of experiment, catalyst mass and initial concentration of H_2O_2 , respectively.

Results of analysis of variance (**Table S3** (Supplementary Information)) shows that the proposed regression model is significant with an F-value of 76.59. The calculated F value is greater than the tabulated F value at 0.05 confidence level ($F_{9,5} = 4.77$), indicating that the terms in the empirical model have a significant effect on the MB degradation rate constant. The goodness of fit of the obtained model was checked by the coefficient of determination (R^2), adjusted coefficient of determination (R_{adj}^2) and lack of fit. R^2 and R_{adj}^2 values were obtained to be 0.9928 and 0.9798, respectively.

Fig. 11 illustrates the response surface plots for the relationship between pH, catalyst mass and initial concentration of H_2O_2 on the degradation of MB onto $CuCo_2O_4/N$ -GQDs. In these plots, the response is mapped against two experimental variables while the remaining are fixed at their central levels. **Fig. 11a** shows that the degradation rate constant of MB increases with increase in catalyst mass and H_2O_2 concentration. The increase in k_{obs} is due to the increase in hydroxyl radical formation when H_2O_2 concentration and catalyst amount is increased. **Fig. 11b** presents the influence of the initial concentration of H_2O_2 and the pH values on the degradation rate constant of MB. The results showed that the degradation rate constant of MB increases with increase in pH and initial concentration of H_2O_2 .

In contrast to iron-based catalysts which higher degradation efficiencies is achieved at acidic conditions, the proposed catalyst work in neutral and alkaline conditions. The results clearly reveal that Fenton reaction catalyzed by $CuCo_2O_4/N$ -GQDs shows a remarkable advantage, because a large volume of pollutants which are discharged in environment have neutral or basic pH values. The similar results were also observed for other cobalt-based catalysts.

Fig. 11

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, this work describes the synthesis of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ nanocomposite by two-step solvothermal method. The characterization results demonstrated that N-GQD play an important role in the alteration of morphology, crystallinity and porosity of the resulted nanocomposite. The degradation results showed that $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ catalyst has significant higher degradation rate of MB compared to pristine CuCo_2O_4 . It is believed that the remarkable increase performance of $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ nanocomposite is ascribed mainly to the synergistic effects between dopant and CuCo_2O_4 , higher surface area and improved electron transport kinetics between N-doped GQDs and metal ions including Cu and Co in prepared nanocomposite. The high efficiency of MB, CV and CR degradation catalyzed by the nanocomposites indicated that the $\text{CuCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{N-GQDs}$ can be an effective candidate for the degradation of organic dyes in textile industries.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

Fig. 6

Fig. 7

Fig. 8

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

Fig. 11

